

Changing Roles of Women in the Society and Family – Present & Past

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Abstract

The existence of women over the time in transition or shift from traditional to modern. The role of the woman who used to be adopted only capable of working in the domestic realm, but this time she is able to develop itself in the public sphere. This raises the existence of variants of interest, between the domestic and the public sphere. This study used a qualitative research method with case study approach. The theory used in this research is by using the concept of rational choice of James Coleman. The purpose of this research is to describe the existence of a career woman in the family. These results indicate that the existence of career women in the public sphere in the family recognized for their collective agreement concluded between career women with families. Mainly deal agreed with her husband and children. But the deal does not diminish the responsibility of working women in the domestic sphere. Career woman in the village does not neglect its role as a housewife and also as a career woman. Role between domestic and public balanced and collaborate.

Keywords: Existence, Roles, Women Career, Domestic Sphere, Public Sphere

Introduction

Women are the pioneers of nation. Indian culture attaches great importance to women, comprising half of world's population. According to a report of secretary general of United Nations, women constitute 50% of human resources, the greatest human resource next only to man having great potentiality.

Women are the key to sustainable development and quality of life in the family. The varieties of role the women assume in the family are those of wife, leader, administrator, manager of family income and last but not the least important the mother.

Role of women in the Today's Society

William Shakespeare said about women that “The world would be imperfect without the presence of the woman. The woman came out of man's rib, not from the feet to be trampled on, not from his head to be superior but from the side to be equal, under the arm to be protected, next to the heart to be loved”. Intelligently Shakespeare said a great truth: you cannot be a couple if one has to carry on their shoulders the other. Quite soon ‘the one who lies beneath, who carry on the other, begins to feel the weight, and he or she gives a good shake and throws the partner down. It would be different if you were walking side by side, with respect and love.

The position of women in the society, and particularly in relation to man, has had over millennia many facets. And now there seems to be semblance of equality but fictitious. Constraints of a much too close past are too deeply rooted. Women find themselves suspended between the real self-consciousness and the conditioning of a society has made of them. It is a situation of great confusion. The message of the media paint a picture of the female stereotype and out of the reality and the woman while is trying to imitate these stereotypes built for the needs of the market is losing her essence.

At the dawn of civilization, the woman has had a great importance and in fact there was a kind of matriarchal social system. The population engaged in agriculture knew the value and sacredness of the feminine and had a very deep concept of the Mother bearer of life. Beginning with the Mother Earth that nourished from birth to old age, supporting the weight of their footsteps, and welcomed them maternal in her womb at the time of the final step. Over the time, the power of the woman, Mother, Goddess, Shakti, Energy was considered a threat by the male and in the thousands of years, for fear of this great feminine energy, man has always tried to diminish her importance going so far as to convince the woman to be a by-product of nature

Role of Woman in Family

The role of women in society, in particular, in the family is dual: first in their parents' house and after that in their husband's home. The circumstances under which the birth of a daughter was considered unwelcome have changed, and although the treatment meted out to a daughter in Indian society is still not on par with that of a son, she is not denied care and affection by her parents.

Changing Role of Women

If we divide society and view it as a modern one and an old- fashioned one, we might fool ourselves and make ourselves feel better at the same time. The roles of women have come in varied forms as they've occupied more visibility, space and varied roles in the modern society talking in the context of Nepal. The varied roles have certainly brought in pressures too as women juggleba modern society, its expectations and old-fashioned elders and individuals who coexist in this modern spectrum.

Whilst it is important to acknowledge these advances, the bigger picture is of the old-fashioned society that we largely live in and around. The changing roles of women has enabled and empowered many and I truly believe that we need to combine such positive and progressive energies of all genders together to ensure that this changing role of women is not only limited to the "modern society" but taken to societies across the country in a suitable manner.

Having visited rural eld locations where many skills were being taught to women, I often wondered how meaningful it would have been for them to have a woman in my position. Unfortunately, even our group from the city of ce consisted of just men.

Visibility of a woman in a respectable and in uential position should not only be for the city as the communities outside the city are desperately waiting for more positive examples of what a woman can achieve. We will only experience and see a bigger change in the role of women once we view society as a whole.

As a Wife

Woman is man's helpmate, partner and comrade. She sacrificeshher personal pleasure and ambitions, sets standard of morality, relieves stress and strain, tension of husband, maintains peace and order in the household. Thereby she creates necessary environment for her male partner to think more about the economic upliftment of family. She is the source of inspiration to man for high endeavour and worth achievements in life.

She stands by him in all the crises as well as she shares with him all successes and attainments. She is the person to whom he turns for love, sympathy, understanding, comfort and recognition. She is the symbol of purity, faithfulness and submission and devotion to her husband.

As an Administrator and Leader of the Household

A well-ordered disciplined household is essential to normal family life. The woman in the family assumes this function. She is the chief executive of an enterprise. She assigns duties among family members according to their interest and abilities and provides resources in-term of equipment and materials to accomplish the job.

She plays a key role in the preparation and serving of meals, selection and care of clothing, laundering, furnishing and maintenance of the house. As an administrator, she organizes various social functions in the family for social development. She also acts as a director of recreation. She plans various recreational activities to meet the needs of young and old members of the family.

As a Manager of Family Income

Woman acts as the humble manager of the family income. It is her responsibility to secure maximum return from every pye spent. She always prefers to prepare a surplus budget instead of a deficit budget. She is very calculating loss and gain while spending money. She distributes judiciously the income on different heads such as necessities, comforts and luxuries. The woman in the family also contributes to the family income through her own earning within or outside the home. She has positive contribution to the family income by the work. She herself performs in the home and uses waste products for productive purposes.

As a Mother

The whole burden of child bearing and greater part of child rearing task are carried out by the woman in the family. She is primarily responsible for the child's habit of self-control, orderliness, industriousness, theft or honesty. Her contacts with the child during the most formative period ofhis development sets up his behaviour pattern. She is thus responsible for the maintenance of utmost discipline in the family.

She is the first teacher of the child. She transmits social heritage to the child. It is from mother that the child learns the laws of the race, the manner of men, moral code and ideals. The mother, because of her intimate and sustained contact with the child, she is able to discover and nurture child's special traits aptitudes and attitudes which subsequently play a key role in the shaping of his personality.

As a mother she is the family health officer. She is very much concerned about the physical wellbeing of every member of the family, the helpless infant, the sickly child, the adolescent youth, and senescent parent. She organizes the home and its activities in such a way so that each member of the family has proper food, adequate sleep and sufficient recreation. She made the home a place of quite comfortable and appropriate setting for the children through her talent. Besides, she cultivates taste in interior design and arrangement, so that the home becomes an inviting, restful and cheerful place.

The mother is the central personality of the home and the family circle. All the members turn to her for sympathy, understanding and recognition. Woman devotes her time, labour and thought for the welfare of the members of the family. For the unity of interacting personalities, man provides the temple woman provides the ceremonies and the atmosphere.

The woman performs the role of wife, partner, organizer, administrator, director, re-creator, disburser, economist, mother, disciplinarian, teacher, health officer, artist and queen in the family at the same time. Apart from it, woman plays a key role in the socio-economic development of the society.

Modern education and modern economic life use to compel woman more and more to leave the narrow sphere of the family circle and work side by side for the enrichment of society. She can be

member of any women's organisation and can launch various programmes like literacy programme such as adult education, education for disadvantaged girls etc.

The purpose of introducing such literacy programme is to raise the society as education enables women to respond to opportunities, to challenge their traditional roles and to change their life circumstances. Education is the most important instrument for human resource development.

Women are the key to sustainable development and quality of life. So they should be members of community centre or club to disseminate knowledge about handicraft, cottage industries, food preservation and low cost nutritious diet to people belonging low socio economic status for their economic upliftment. They should act as leaders of the society to raise voice against women violence, exploitation in household as well as in work place, dowry prohibition superstition and other social atrocities.

They should be member of religious institution to deliver spiritual speech to adolescent boys and girls in order to eliminate juvenile delinquency problem from the society. In addition they have pivotal role in pre and post marital counselling for adolescent girl regarding sexual transmitted disease. AIDS and other infectious diseases. They are supposed to create awareness about Human rights, women and child rights, credit facility of bank, different immunization programmes to low socio economic status people of the society.

Moreover it is the women who have sustained the growth of society and moulded the future of nations. In the emerging complex social scenario, women have a vital role to play in different sectors. They can no longer be considered as mere harbingers of peace but are emerging as the source of power and symbol of progress.

Conclusion

“The role of women is always changing it always has been. Although I have always thought of the roles of women in a positive way regardless of whether she is a homemaker or a working woman or both. I appreciate the women in my lives that have always inspired me and I am thankful that I can always look up to them. However, the society has not always been appreciative of them in the past and while the situation is changing we still have a long way to go. While it is a long shot, I hope we live in a better future where gender is just a biological aspect and everyone works together in every eld. The discrimination that women faced in the past and the pain and hardships it caused was the reason that the society is still patriarchal to this day. But now, she has been doing her own thing and I still am grateful that we are slowly evolving to a liberal society. I hope she does what she wants to do and all of us get rid of the patriarchal attitude that takes us nowhere in the future, I just want everyone to open their eyes and minds and learn to appreciate her more for her contributions.”

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